

Green Economy: Sistematic Literatur Review

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to reveal how research topics and issues regarding the Green Economy are developing. The research method used was Systematic Literature Review (SLR) with VOS Viewer Data Analysis Software. The articles reviewed were 429 articles sourced from the Scopus database. The research results show that the development of research topics and issues regarding the Green Economy reflects a positive evolution in understanding of environmental and sustainability challenges in the context of the global economy. Involving researchers from various countries, this research focuses on topic clusters that develop along with socio-economic needs and dynamics. Wang J., as the main contributor with the largest number of articles, discusses major issues such as environmental pollution, carbon emissions, and environmentally friendly tourism.

INTRODUCTION

The green economy is a concept that is increasingly gaining global attention as a response to the environmental and economic challenges facing the world today. This concept is increasingly becoming a fundamental policy in sustainable development (Kinda, 2021). Policy certainty will always have a positive impact on the country's economy, and vice versa (Ma et al., 2022). In an era of uncertain climate change and concerns about the sustainability of natural resources, the green economy has become an attractive solution. It represents a new economic paradigm that focuses on sustainable growth, a clean environment, and efficiency in the use of natural resources. And it is also necessary to understand that the complexity of economic problems between dynamic economic growth and preserving the natural environment in the long term has not yet been able to overcome it (Steblyanskaya et al., 2021).

A green economy involves a fundamental transformation of how we understand and manage our economy. It's not just about reducing carbon emissions or reducing waste, but also about creating new jobs, developing innovative technologies and ensuring social justice. In recent decades, countries and companies have initiated steps towards a green economy by incorporating sustainable economic practices and green technologies into their economic strategies. A number of previous studies have examined various topics and problems related to the Green Economy. Pliavskiy, revealed that several countries are worried and believe that shifting the economy towards a green economy could hamper the country's development due to differences in green economy instruments and principles for each country (Pliavskiy et al., 2021). Research by Liu in China shows that expanding financial inclusion can contribute to increasing environmentally friendly economic capabilities (Z. Liu et al., 2022). Furthermore, research conducted by Kinda shows that green economy indicators have a controversial impact on food security (food availability and the proportion of the population who are malnourished) in 35 African countries. Biofuels contribute to reducing food security, while renewable energy increases food security and carbon dioxide emissions have no effect on food security (Kinda, 2021).

Although many previous studies have reviewed the green economy, not many have adopted the approach *Systematic Literature Review* (SLR) and the Vosviewer application to analyze it. Therefore, this research focuses on exploring the green economy using the SLR approach through VOSviewer application data analysis. The SLR approach is a literature review method that allows a more systematic understanding of research topics and themes.

The focus of this research study is on efforts to answer the question of how research topics and issues regarding the Green Economy are developing. The research method is *Sistematic Literature Review* (SLR) with VOSviewer Data Analysis Software. The study category consists of several categories, namely researcher (Author), Country (Countries), topic cluster (Network Visualization), topic discussion time (Overlay Visualization), and dominant topic (Density Visualization). This research contributes to the direction of green economic

research development. Apart from that, it can also be used as a reference for government development and policies related to economic transition.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Green Economy Concept

Green Economy is a concept and approach to economic development that places environmental sustainability as the main goal. The green economy focuses on the sustainable use of natural resources, reducing waste, and protecting against environmental damage (Vishnevsky et al., 2021). The green economy aims to improve human welfare, social equality, and reduce environmental risks (Chaaben et al., 2022).

The main principle of a green economy is to integrate economic, social and environmental aspects in every decision and policy taken. These principles include reducing carbon emissions, which can be implemented through efficiency, increasing renewable energy, reducing deforestation, increasing sustainable transportation, efficient waste management, and increasing awareness and education (Vishnevsky et al., 2021). Apart from reducing carbon emissions, resource efficiency and the use of renewable energy are also important parts of the green economy principles. Resource efficiency prioritizes the use of resources wisely and optimally. In this context, resource efficiency includes efforts to reduce waste, minimize waste, and maximize economic output by using fewer inputs. Meanwhile, the principle of using renewable energy aims to reduce dependence on fossil energy resources which are limited and have the potential to damage the environment. Renewable energy, such as solar, wind, hydro and geothermal power, has the advantage of being naturally renewable and having a lower environmental impact compared to fossil fuels (Vishnevsky et al., 2021).

Green economic growth can have a positive impact on the economy, namely increasing social welfare and reducing the risk of environmental damage (Green Economy and Low Carbon Development Encourage Economic Growth and Improve Social Welfare - Coordinating Ministry for Economic Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia, n.d.). The application of the green economy concept can open up new opportunities for economic sectors, such as the renewable energy sector, waste management and the development of environmentally friendly technology. Apart from that, green economic growth can also create new jobs and increase productivity. However, it is important to remember that implementing a green economy is not always easy and requires support from various parties, including the government, society and the private sector. Apart from that, it is also necessary to evaluate the impact of the green economy on other economic sectors, such as the conventional energy sector and the agricultural sector (Parmawati, 2019).

The Relevance of Sustainable Development in the Context of a Green Economy Sustainable development is very relevant in the context of a green economy because the goal of a green economy is to achieve sustainable economic growth without damaging the environment and improving the social welfare of society. The Indonesian government, as one of the countries that is

concerned about the green economy, has established a green economy plan as one of the main strategies for economic transformation in the medium to long term to accelerate economic recovery after the Covid-19 pandemic, as well as encourage the creation of inclusive and sustainable economic development. One form of green economy that will be implemented is the implementation of a carbon price policy in the form of carbon cap and trade, as well as a carbon tax scheme in 2024. Apart from that, green economic growth can also create new jobs and increase

productivity. The concepts of green economy and green growth emerged in response to the need to adopt a more integrated and comprehensive approach, in combining social and environmental factors in the economic process, with the aim of achieving sustainable development (Green Economy Encourages the Creation of Inclusive and Sustainable Economic Development - Coordinating Ministry for Economic Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia, n.d.). Green economic growth can also have a positive impact on the economy, namely increasing social welfare and reducing the risk of environmental damage. The application of the green economy concept can open up new opportunities for economic sectors, such as the renewable energy sector, waste management and the development of environmentally friendly technology. Apart from that, green economic growth can also encourage economic growth and improve social welfare while maintaining environmental quality. Implementing a green economy is not always easy and requires support from various parties, including the government, society and the private sector. It is also necessary to evaluate the impact of the green economy on other economic sectors, such as the conventional energy sector and the agricultural sector.

Sustainable development is very relevant in the context of a green economy because the goal of a green economy is to achieve sustainable economic growth without damaging the environment and improving the social welfare of society. The concept of a green economy emerged in response to the need to adopt a more integrated and comprehensive approach, in combining social and environmental factors in the economic process, with the aim of achieving sustainable development. The application of the green economy concept can open up new opportunities for economic sectors, such as the renewable energy sector, waste management and the development of environmentally friendly technology. Apart from that, green economic growth can also create new jobs and increase productivity (Green Growth and Sustainability: Implementation for Resilient Indonesian Cities, n.d.)

Research Findings

In an era of increasing digitalization, the role of manufacturing technology becomes crucial in creating environmentally friendly economic conditions, especially for developing countries where industrial innovation is still limited (Vishnevsky et al., 2021). Along with this, research on the green economy is increasingly dominant in developed countries, marking increasing recognition in the academic field of the importance of the transition to a sustainable economy (Alsmadi & Alzoubi, 2022).

Manufacturing technology has a significant impact on an environmentally friendly national economy. Developing countries, which often lag behind in industrial innovation, face the challenge of increasing the level of manufacturing technology to support environmental sustainability (Vishnevsky et al., 2021). On the other hand, developed countries dominate research on the green economy and give increasing recognition to the importance of transitioning towards a sustainable economic model (Alsmadi & Alzoubi, 2022). In this context, technology transfer, especially Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), plays an important role in the advancement of green economic technology. Nevertheless, complex challenges in the field of international investment law are still obstacles in technology transfer for the green economy (Ma, 2022).

The importance of the transition to a green economy is increasingly recognized as a crucial step in achieving economic, social and environmental sustainability. The European Union's commitment to the challenge environment and the transition to a green economy shows an active role in responding to global issues related to sustainability (Mentes, 2024). This is also reflected in higher levels of environmental patents, lower CO₂ emissions, and stricter environmental policies in higher ranking countries (Mealy & Teytelboym, 2022). At the regional level in China, several provinces are making efforts to improve the degradation of natural assets through the formulation of new policies that support the green economy (Steblyanskaya et al., 2021). Thus, it is important for each region to form a core industrial cluster model in the digital economy to facilitate environmentally friendly development (P. Li et al., 2022).

Apart from technological and policy aspects, green values and educational support are key factors in forming positive perceptions of green entrepreneurship. Applying green values and an educational approach can be a starting point for building the younger generation's understanding of sustainable development (Nuringsih & Nuryasman, 2021). In Africa, the contribution of biofuels to decreasing food security shows the complexity of the challenges in the region, while renewable energy is considered as one solution to increasing food security (Kinda, 2021). Overall, this article illustrates the role of diverse elements, from technology and policy to green values and education, in embracing the transition to a sustainable green economy.

The description above provides an illustration that the Green Economy is an economic development concept whose main aim is to achieve environmental sustainability by integrating economic, social and environmental aspects. Its main principles involve reducing carbon emissions, resource efficiency, and the use of renewable energy. Green economic growth is expected to improve social welfare, reduce environmental risks, and create new opportunities, especially in the renewable energy and environmentally friendly technology sectors. Although implementing a green economy requires cross-sector support, evaluation of impacts on other sectors, and awareness of the challenges that may be faced, sustainable development in the context of a green economy becomes very relevant. The goal is to achieve sustainable economic growth without damaging the environment and improving social welfare. Green economic growth not only has a positive impact on the economy, but also opens

up new opportunities for the renewable energy sector, waste management and the development of environmentally friendly technologies.

In the era of rapidly developing digitalization, manufacturing technology plays an important role in creating environmentally friendly economic conditions, especially for developing countries where industrial innovation is still limited. Although developing countries are faced with the challenge of increasing the level of manufacturing technology, technology transfer, especially in the context of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), is identified as a key element in the technological progress of the green economy. Although the complexity of international investment law is an obstacle, the importance of the transition to a green economy is recognized as a crucial step in achieving economic, social and environmental sustainability, as reflected in the European Union's commitments and environmental policies at the global level. In addition to technology and policy, green values and educational support were identified as key factors in shaping positive perceptions of green entrepreneurship, while the contribution of biofuels and renewable energy in Africa shows the complexity of the challenges in the region. From the description above, overall it confirms the importance of various elements, starting from technology and policies to green values and education, in embracing the transition towards a sustainable green economy. To support this, it is necessary to carry out various research efforts, especially in presenting developments in green economy topics and issues.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses the Systematic Literature Review method. The Systematic Literature Review (SLR) research method is a scientific methodological approach that systematically summarizes primary research results to present more comprehensive and balanced facts. This method is used because in this research the researcher seeks to reveal how green economic topics and issues develop based on systematic research results.

The research stage begins with determining the research topic. Data was obtained centrally in the Scopus database with two keywords, namely "Economy" and "Green". After the data was obtained, the data was then selected based on 2021 and 2022, resulting in 429 documents obtained (table 1). Data from 429 documents was exported in RIS and CSV form, then analyzed using the VOSviewer application. Analysis of the VOSviewer application focuses on 5 stages, namely Researcher (Author), Country (Country), Topic Cluster (Network Visualization), Latest Topics (Overlay Visualization), and Dominant and Non-Dominant Topics (Density Visualization). After that, it is described in the form of results and discussion, then a conclusion is given.

RESEARCH RESULT

Author

Researchers included in the calculation for this research are researchers who have at least 3 articles about Green Economy in the Scopus database. The results of VOSviewer data processing show that there are 11 clusters with a total of 20 researchers. The highest number of articles is 5 documents owned by

Wang j. For researchers named Ullah s., Li x., Zhang l., Ngo t.q., Wang y., and Yu z. each has 4 article documents. Meanwhile, Irfan has the highest number of Citations

m. a total of 178 quotes. These authors are also connected and unconnected, both within the internal cluster and external cluster (Table 2). Author relationships can be caused by joint authorship in a scientific article published in the Scopus database.

Table 2. Number of Articles, Citations, and Researcher Relations

Author	Document	Citations	Total Link Strength	Cluster	Writing Relationship	
					Internal Cluster	Cluster External
Ozturk i.	3	54	3	1	Ullah s., Li x.	-
Allah s.	4	67	3	1	Wu h., Ozturk i.	-
Li x.	4	30	1	1	Ozturk i.	-
Wu h.	3	17	1	1	Allah s.	-
Money j.	5	27	3	2	Chen z., Liu y.	Zhang l.
Chen z.	3	5	2	2	Money j.	Zhang l.
Liu y.	3	17	1	2	Money j.	-
Zhang l.	4	20	4	3	Wang c., Zhang j.	Wang j., Chen z.
Money c.	3	15	2	3	Zang l., Zhang j.	-
Zhang j.	3	32	2	3	Wang c., Zhang l.	-
Lyulyov o.	3	28	3	4	Pimonenko t.	-
Pimonenko t.	3	28	3	4	Lyulyov o.	-
Irfan m.	3	178	1	5	Suksatan v.	-

Suksatan v.	3	145	1	5	Irfan m.	-
Li y.	3	69	0	6	-	-
Ngo t.q.	4	51	0	7	-	-
Streimikien d.	3	40	0	8	-	-
Wang y.	4	66	0	9	-	-
Yu z.	4	109	0	10	-	-
Zhu z.	3	56	0	11	-	-

Source: Process Vosviewer data

Latest Researchers

The next stage is about the novelty of the researcher. Researcher novelty is intended to analyze the latest researchers based on VOSviewer results. Based on the results of the analysis, researchers named Ozturk i., Ullah s., Li x., Wu h., are classified as the newest researchers, namely in 2022. The focus of the topics they raised was agriculture and CO2 emissions (Zhou et al., 2022) , and environmentally friendly innovation (L. Liu et al., 2022). Apart from them, another relatively new researcher is Li y. and Liu y. with a focus on the digital economy (Y. Li et al., 2022). Most of these researchers are not only classified as the newest researchers but also consistently as dominant researchers, only Li y. categorized as non-dominant researchers. Apart from Li y. Other researchers who are not dominant include Zhu z., and Streimikiene d.

Dominant Researcher

Countries

Country determination is determined by the criteria of having a minimum of 3 articles. Based on VOSviewer's analysis, the country with the largest number of studies is China, with 96 article documents, followed by the United Kingdom with 52 documents, Germany and Pakistan with 35 documents each. Meanwhile, the countries with the least number of studies, namely Nigeria, Croatia, South Korea and New Zealand, each have 3 document articles (Figure 3). China has indeed become one of the leaders in research on the Green Economy. China has invested heavily in efforts to reduce the environmental impact of its economic growth and develop green technologies. They have designed various programs and initiatives to address issues such as air pollution, sustainable energy use and environmental protection.

Country Distribution

China's success in making an economic transition has encouraged other countries to take part in the green economy. In the VOSviewer Overlay Visualization section, countries that are starting to implement the latest green economy include Pakistan, Malaysia, Turkey, Vietnam, Taiwan, Saudi Arabia and Brazil. Meanwhile, countries that have long adopted the Green Economy concept are Sweden, France, Ukraine and Indonesia. The implementation of the green economy in these countries is not as massive as China's.

Research Topic Clusters (Network Visualization)

Network Visualization is one part of the VOSviewer application to determine the distribution of topic clusters. Based on the results of the analysis, the topic of "Green Economy" is spread into 6 research topic clusters.

Topic Clusters

First Cluster:In the first cluster, the topic of Economic Growth is the central topic which is connected not only to its own cluster but also to topics in other clusters. In the cluster, the topic of Economic Growth is connected to the study of other topics including Relationship, Emission, Evidence, Carbon Emission, and Energy Efficiency.

Distribution of Cluster Topics 1

These topics are among the topics that are widely studied by researchers. There are quite a lot of topics that are classified as less studied by researchers, namely Variation, Globalization, Energy Use, Finance. Development, Environmental Sustainability, and Short Run. Meanwhile, Economic Growth studies are connected to other topic clusters, including China, Region, Innovation, Covid, Circular Economy, Implementation, Pandemic, and Energy Consumption. Economic Growth is the central topic of study in Green Economy research. This is because Green Economy is an economic concept that offers environmentally friendly development. Many countries have succeeded in making this concept a new alternative for development that has a direct impact on economic growth, for example China. Causing the topic of Economic Growth to become central and directly related to many other topics across clusters.

Second Cluster: In the second cluster, the topic of Circular Economy is the biggest topic and has been studied most by researchers. The distribution is connected to research on internal clusters and external clusters. Internal cluster topics that are directly connected to the Circular Economy and are of great interest to researchers include Implementation, Opportunity, Enterprise, Challenge and Transformation. Meanwhile, those who are not very interested in studying are topics about Green Logistics, Circularity, Accounts, Economic Activity, and Smes. The Circular Economy topic is also directly connected to research studies outside the cluster, including Covid, Practice, Barrier, Firm, Performance, Supply Chain, and Innovation

Distribution of Cluster Topics 2

Third Cluster:The research topic most popular with researchers in the third cluster is Performance. Within the cluster itself, this topic is directly connected to several study topics including Innovation, Practice, Firm, Green Innovation, Covid, CSR, Barriers, and Theory. These topics are of great interest to research by researchers. Meanwhile, topics that are still lacking research interest in this cluster include Green Performance, Green Practice, Blockchain Technology, Manufacturers, Policy Makers, and Environmental Concern. For cross-cluster topics, the Performance topic is directly connected to study topics that are considered to be in high demand, including Green Investment, Policymaker, Evidence, Relationship, Variable, Carbon Emission, Emission, China, Region, Implementation, and Circular Economy. Meanwhile, it is

relatively small His interests include study topics regarding Carbon Neutrality, Construction Enterprise, Researcher, Green Bond.

Distribution of Cluster Topics 3

Fourth Cluster: Research interest in the fourth cluster is still very minimal, there are no research topics that are very prominent within the cluster, except in other clusters connected to this cluster. In the internal cluster, the Green Bond research topic is the topic that is most researched and is directly related to study topics about Instruments, Investors, Green Bond Market, Economic Benefits, Green, and Low Carbon Economy. Meanwhile, across clusters, the topic of this study is directly connected to Performance, Price, Evidence, Oil and China, and is classified as research that has relatively great interest among researchers.

Distribution of Cluster Topics 4

Fifth Cluster: Internally, this cluster shows that the situation of the topic is not too dominant, and is relatively relative. The topic of Price is the only topic that is most directly connected to the study of other topics. The Price topic is directly connected to the study topics of Demand, Climate Policy, Significant Impact, and Energy Consumption. Meanwhile, cross-clusters that are of great interest include Covid, Supply Chain, Relationship, Evidence, Variable and Carbon Emission. Topics with less research interest include GDP, Short Run, and Foreign Direct Investment

Distribution of Cluster Topics 5

Sixth Cluster: Researcher interest in the sixth cluster is quite large, especially the topic of China. These two topics are central topics that are directly connected not only within the internal cluster but also spread throughout the cluster. Within the internal cluster, the topic of China is directly connected to the study of the topic Region and Digital Economy which is considered to be of great interest to research by researchers. Apart from that, the topic of China is also connected to study topics that are classified as having minimal research interest, including Construction Enterprise, Green Development, Green Credit, GTFP, Core Industry Agglomeration, and Agglomeration. In contrast to its relationship with study topics outside the cluster, the China topic is directly connected to topics that have a great research interest, including Performance, Practice, Covid, Green Innovation, Innovation, Challenge, Opportunity, Relationship, Economic Growth, Emission, Carbon Emission, and Green Financial.

Research Novelty (Overlay Visualization)

The results of the VOSviewer analysis, if seen from the Newness of Research (Overlay Visualization), show that the latest research on Green Economy is around the end of 2021. The latest study topics on the Green Economy research theme include Price, Barrier, Green Practice, Financial Inclusion, and Green Development. Meanwhile, the oldest study topics include Practice, with other topics connected to it such as Opportunity, Green Building, and Eco Innovation. Apart from that, there are Regions with derivative topics such as Green Technology, digitalization, and Pandemic. Latest Topics.

Price: The study topic of Relationship is one of the main topics that connects the study with the topic of Price. Many researchers have tried to connect the topic of Relationship with Price, especially its influence on the country's economy, for example the relationship between investment and oil prices and carbon emissions, concluding that direct investment is positively related to carbon emissions in the long term, and oil prices have a positive effect and significant impact on CO₂ emissions (Ashraf et al., 2022). Apart from Relationship, researchers also try to connect the topic of Performance with Price. One of them is research conducted by M Deng which links economic performance with the prices of natural resource commodities. The results conclude that natural resource price volatility has a negative impact on economic performance (Deng, 2022).

Barrier: A relatively new topic is Barrier. The study topic of Practice is a big topic and connects it with the relatively new Barrier study topic. Many researchers have attempted to connect the study topic of Practice with the Barrier topic, as was done by Prasad and his friends. He is looking for obstacles in implementing sustainable Lean-Led Manufacturing practices and the potential for using Blockchain Technology in overcoming obstacles. The result is that economic and managerial barriers, knowledge and awareness barriers and organizational barriers are the most prominent categories of barriers to sustainable manufacturing (Prasad et al., 2022).

Financial Inclusion: In the Green Economy theme, the study topic of Financial Inclusion is a topic that is quite popular with researchers. Based on the analysis results, the topic of Financial Inclusion is present in order to answer the contribution of the Green Economy to financial practices. It must be understood that the role of financial inclusion in promoting a sustainable environment is still very minimally researched. The researchers also concluded that financial inclusion contributes to increasing CO₂ emissions. (Tufail et al., 2022) In addition, financial inclusion is very important for improving the country's performance and the green economy. Its existence contributes to increasing green economic capabilities in China (Z. Liu et al., 2022). Meanwhile, in ASEAN countries, financial inclusion contributes to the amount of pollution removed from the environment (Saydaliev & Chin, 2022).

Green Development: The topic of study on Green Development is still relatively new and there are still very few researchers who have covered this topic. This means that there is still a very big opportunity for future researchers to study it. There are three topics that connect his research to the topic of Green Development, namely China, Digital Economy, and City. Green Economy is an alternative development program in development economic practice amidst the rise of conventional development programs that ignore the negative impacts they cause.

Dominant Topic(Density Visualization)

VOSviewer analysis on Density Visualization to find out dominant and non-dominant topics in the Green Economy research theme. The brighter the color shown indicates that the topic has been predominantly researched, and vice versa, if the color is faded, it indicates that the topic is still minimally

researched. This means that the space for research on this topic is still open.

Dominant Research Topics

The analysis results show that there are many dominant research topics. These topics include China, Covid, and Economic Growth.

China: The green economy is emerging as one of the dominant factors in ecological sustainability as well as a new alternative in the country's economy. China is a country that is experiencing an economic transformation towards a green economy. Green development is China's national development plan since 2008 and has invested huge resources to maintain the transition to a green economy. (*Partnership with China | UNEP - UN Environment Programme*, n.d.) Because of this, researchers are very enthusiastic in studying the practice of China's economic transition towards a green economy with various related topics. So that is the reason the topic of China is considered dominant.

Dominant Topic

Covid: The Covid outbreak that emerged in 2019 has had a huge negative impact on the country's economy. Limited space for movement and interaction forced the economy to reach its lowest point in all countries. This situation was triggered by the paralysis of economic practices, including the green economy sector. This has attracted the attention of researchers to study the development of the green economy during Covid conditions and after.

Economic Growth: Over the last two decades, countries have been so worried about facing environmental problems, climate change and global warming which have had a real negative impact on people's lives. The trigger is the incessant development policies that are not environmentally friendly and only prioritize economic interests. On this basis, the green economy concept appears as the right step in resolving this problem. Many countries have implemented the green economy concept and made it an important instrument for economic growth. Since this concept began to be campaigned until now, many researchers are interested in examining the contribution of the green economy to a country's economic growth. These researchers include Saqib, (Saqib, 2022) Kolmykova, (Kolmykova et al., 2021) and Viktorovna. (Viktorovna et al., 2021) The large number of interested researchers shows the dominance of the topic of Economic Growth.

Research Topic is Not Dominant

The non-dominant topic in the Green Economic theme shows that there is a lot of room to study it further. In the context of the Green Economy, these topics include CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility), Green Credit, GTFP (Green Trade Finance Program), Digital Economy, Energy Use, Financial Development, and Green Logistics. In more understanding in depth towards the Green Economy, each of these topics has great potential to make a significant contribution to developing sustainable economic practices. Therefore, further research and exploration of these topics will help us understand how these aspects can play a role in achieving the goal of a more sustainable green economy in the future.

DISCUSSION

The concept of a green economy was born as a response to growing concerns regarding the negative impact of industrialization and traditional economic growth on the environment and sustainability through its basic principle, namely integrating economic, social and environmental aspects in every decision and policy taken. To perfect the success of green economic values, support from various parties is needed, one of which is researchers. Wang J. is the only researcher with the most articles. He focuses on several big green economy issues such as environmental pollution (Xie et al., 2022), carbon emissions (Dong et al., 2021), and green tourism (Zhang et al., 2021). The development of researchers on the Green Economy continues with new researchers bringing focus to new aspects such as agriculture, CO2 emissions, environmentally friendly innovation, and the digital economy. According to Parmawati, the researchers' contribution is used as material for evaluating green economic development (Parmawati, 2019).

The concept of a green economy has emerged as a new alternative in economic development models. China has become a country that is very massive in diverting economic development to a green economic approach. China's implementation of a green economy is triggered by a number of significant reasons. First, environmental issues have become an increasingly pressing global concern, and China, as a country with a large population and high level of industrialization, feels the need to reduce its negative impact on the environment. Industrial technology in forming an environmentally friendly economy is very crucial, as stated by Vishnevsky (Vishnevsky et al., 2021). Second, the green economy is expected to open up new opportunities for long-term economic growth, by investing in environmentally friendly sectors such as renewable energy, sustainable transportation and green technology. Third, with its dependence on natural resource imports, China is also seeking ways to increase the sustainability of its resources and reduce its vulnerability to global price fluctuations. Therefore, China has taken various steps, including the development of stricter environmental regulations, the promotion of environmentally friendly technologies, and large investments in renewable energy, to achieve these green economy goals.

In 2013, *United Nations Environment Programme* (UNEP) and China's Ministry of Environmental Protection jointly published the study *China's Green Long March*, which assessed China's progress towards a green economy and found that China has seen particularly strong green developments in solar Photovoltaic, wind, bioenergy, cement, and industrial environments over the past decade. Report *Modeling China's Green Economy 2010-2050*, also launched by UNEP in collaboration with *Institute of Scientific and Technical Information of China*, and shows that China's steps to transition to a green economy will be beneficial for economic growth, climate change mitigation, job creation, and improving the living standards of the poor, as well as providing policy recommendations for prioritizing China's green economy (*Partnership with China | UNEP - UN Environment Programme*, n.d.). China's success in making an economic transition has encouraged other countries to

take part in the green economy. Countries that are starting to implement the latest green economy include Pakistan, Malaysia, Turkey, Vietnam, Taiwan, Saudi Arabia and Brazil. Meanwhile, countries that have long adopted the Green Economy concept are Sweden, France, Ukraine and Indonesia. The implementation of the green economy in these countries is not as massive as China's. However, this is sufficient evidence that both developed and developing countries consider it important to carry out a sustainable economic transition (Alsmadi & Alzoubi, 2022), although developing countries have challenges in the form of industrial technological innovation (Vishnevsky et al., 2021).

Another potential that encourages economic improvement through a green economy is the birth of a microeconomic spirit in reducing pressure on the environment (Circular Economy). Because of its large impact on GDP, microeconomics is receiving great attention in several countries, especially regarding governance, relations with stakeholders, and innovation, to accelerate the transition towards circularity (Gennari, 2022), even though it encounters many obstacles, one of which is community culture (Neves & Marques, 2022). As the green economy develops, discussions about the green economy are not limited to its direct impact on the economy. Latest, topics about *Price, Barrier, Green Practice, Financial Inclusion, dan Green Development* has become a topic that has been intensively studied and is in direct contact with one of the principles of a green economy, namely resource efficiency to avoid waste. The form of implementation is such as green bonds which can be realized through the role of energy prices and environmentally friendly energy shares (Yan et al., 2022). Other forms of implementation such as financial inclusion. Financial inclusion in the context of a green economy refers to efforts to ensure that all levels of society, including those at a low economic level or have limited access to financial services, can participate in and benefit from green economic development. In several countries, financial inclusion contributes to the creation of CO₂ emissions which are a factor in environmental degradation (Lin & Wu, 2022). This proves that financial inclusion cannot always contribute well to a green economy as found by Liu Z. in China.

Throughout its existence, the green economy concept has contributed a lot to a country's economic development because it emphasizes sustainable growth in order to improve people's welfare. Due to the large contribution of the green economy to the economy, the topic of economic growth has become very dominant in research. When the economy experiences a recession as experienced during Covid-19, economic principles through the green economy can encourage the acceleration of economic recovery after Covid-19. The pandemic has exposed vulnerabilities in the global economic system and highlighted the urgency to restructure development models that are more resilient to future crises.

The green economy offers a framework that prioritizes environmental

sustainability, resource efficiency, and green technological innovation. Through investments in sectors such as renewable energy, sustainable transportation, and smart waste management, countries can create new jobs, increase economic resilience, and reduce negative impacts on the environment. In addition, focusing on a green economy can increase global competitiveness, strengthen energy independence, and reduce dependence on limited resources. By embracing the concept of a green economy, countries can rebuild their economic foundations in a way that is more inclusive, sustainable and resilient to future challenges.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The development of research topics and issues on the Green Economy reflects the evolution of understanding of environmental and sustainability challenges in the context of the global economy. Over time, this research involved various researchers from various countries, focusing on topic clusters that developed along with socio-economic needs and dynamics. Wang J., with the largest number of articles, has been a major contributor in understanding major green economy issues, such as environmental pollution, carbon emissions, and green tourism. Meanwhile, the emergence of new researchers, such as Ozturk I., Ullah S., Li At the global level, countries such as China are showing success in implementing a green economic approach, taking concrete steps such as the development of strict environmental regulations and large investments in renewable energy. China's success has encouraged other countries to participate in the green economy, both those that are just starting to adopt it, such as Pakistan and Malaysia, and those that have long implemented this concept, such as Sweden and France. Topic cluster analysis also illustrates the evolution of research issues. Issues regarding economic growth and the Circular Economy have a large portion in research. Meanwhile, issues such as *Price, Barrier, Green Practice, Financial Inclusion, dan Green Development* is the latest study on the green economy which focuses on the implementation of green bonds and financial inclusion. In relation to dominant and non-dominant topics, several very dominant topics are topics about economic growth and Covid-19. Overall, the development of research topics and issues on the Green Economy reflects a positive evolution, with new researchers bringing new perspectives, countries adopting green economy principles, and newly emerging topics enriching the scope of research. This creates a strong foundation for the understanding and implementation of green economy concepts at the global level.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

This research has a contribution to the direction of research development and government policy. The findings of this research provide an empirical basis for understanding the impact of economic practices on the environment as well as the potential for sustainable solutions. This, in turn, provides guidance for researchers to identify topic clusters that are urgent and relevant to be followed up in the form of research.

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The limitation of this research is that the data used is still limited to secondary data types, namely previous articles sourced from the Scopus database. Future research needs to use primary data, namely interview and observation data.

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